

"RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION"

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OPTIMIZING TIME MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES FOR EFFECTIVE READING: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY

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Annotation. *The article closely examines the various time-saving methods that can be employed to boost reading effectiveness. The extensive research offers an in-depth understanding of the methodologies that readers should apply to maximize their study time. As a result, people can attain faster reading paces, reading retention, and comprehension thus spend less time consumed in learning. For those who wish to enhance their culture of reading and get better grades or work better, this is a perfect guide.*

Key words: *reading comprehension, scaffolding, time management in reading, contextualizing, metacognition, teacher support.*

Effective reading is one of the essential skills that help achieve high academic and professional results. Yet, many people find it difficult to combine extensive reading with time management skills. As a result, the current article investigates the problem and identifies the most efficient reading-based time management strategies. By conducting a literature review and collecting the findings from the research, the current paper explores the key aspects of time management integration for successful reading comprehension and activities.

Methodology:

While I was doing my research, I came across such different encounters as "Assessment of Reading Comprehension" by Habib Madani and he stated "The study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative techniques to examine the effectiveness of time management strategies for reading. Qualitative data collection involves interviews and surveys with individuals who actively engage in extensive reading tasks, gathering insights into their current time management practices and challenges faced". As reading comprehension in the current time is becoming something relevant, creativeness can also be fostered by students along the way. In this case there are several steps that teachers can do in the lesson to help students improve their comprehension in reading:

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- Before Reading. This step is also crucial that before starting anything that connects with the reading. Warm-up questions could make students active and of course they should be relevant to the topic. At this stage, teachers should help them get a clear understand of a certain reading.

- Pre-reading stage, teacher should make sure that all students are concentrated and active because the focus is key to the successful comprehension of reading.

- While reading students make sure that they do all the following steps: they should what sort of reading they are doing and what kind of skills or strategies they are going to use; differentiating main topics from the secondary topics; getting the first impression is also a significant step. Making it explicit in this way helps poor readers by making clear what they should be doing and what they were not doing before, or what they were doing wrong (Aaronites, 1991; Rosen shine & Meister, 1997).

- Post reading. After finishing reading, it is important that teacher checks all the students understand the given topic and give feedback to them as some of them may fail to do so. Although conclusion may be drawn in the text, it is worth checking whether students have the same understanding or not.

According to the research held in the 1990s, it is evident that students can learn certain strategies employed by proficient readers, and that when these strategies are taught, students' comprehension and retention of texts tend to improve. There is much less evidence that we know how to teach students to make inferences and to monitor their text comprehension (Pressley, 2002). In most studies, the strategies were taught one at a time (Keene & Zimmermann, 1997).

Another way of dealing with the comprehension is conceptualizing and contextualizing. Students must have the prior knowledge about the topics of reading, and it should be done by teachers. One method called “explicit demonstration or explanation;” they should provide the readers with this strategy. Before the students apply this method to their reading. Teacher can praise or reward if they do it accurately or give them feedback where it is needed.

Do you need a professional way of learning how to improve your comprehension in reading? I found some critically acclaimed methods that can be a supportive guidance to the students:

Metocognition. If you assess metacognitive skills and practice with them, you are highly likely to achieve focus and planning, respectively. “Metacognition is critical for reading success: It contributes to reading comprehension, and it promotes academic learning.” A considerable amount of attention and focus must be paid to

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win this battle (reading an entire text and comprehending it). It might seem ridiculous that some may think “Is it really hard to give you concentration to one text and understand it”. However, if you do your research, it is indeed the problem of many.

When it comes to the evidence that great amount of people fails to achieve decent comprehension, according to New Grattan Institute research suggests that for those students who are hardest hit by poor reading performance and leave school early. The usage of scaffolding enables students to solve problems that they would not have been able to solve without this support. By scaffolding, students can foster the ability to plan out and manage their time efficiently. This, of course, can be done with the guidance and support of the teacher. “Engagement captures ‘the quality of students’ participation with learning activities.” - this plays the most part of learning process. Successfully engaging the students to the lesson and being able to direct their focus, it gives the sense of fulfillment and feeling of satisfaction. Even the most effective strategy and instruction will fail if students lack motivation and engagement, or if they doubt their ability to succeed in what they do. Thus, the emotional support and best engagement from the teacher are needed.

Petition for commitment and future research on improving reading comprehension and managing the time efficiently:

- In today’s world, children, pupils, and students are sometimes distracted and can not focus on one thing at a time, thus the help and guidance from their teachers can change a great deal. Receiving engagement and encouragement from their teachers, promised improvement can be assured from the students equally. Till this day and age, students are having demanding time comprehending what is written on a page and thinking rationally.

- On one hand, the idea of illiteracy can be emerged. This can be seen as example of Australia; thus, business networks are severely affected. 93 % of employers say poor literacy and numeracy impedes their business, according to a 2013 Australian Industry Group survey.

Test for measuring comprehension in reading. It has initially used before. In Netherlands Institute of Educational Measurement. This test has been evaluated by the Commission on Testing Matters (COTAN) of the Netherlands Institute of Psychologists (NIP) and was judged to be “good” on the quality of the principles on which the tests were constructed, the quality of the test material, the quality of the manual, reliability, and construct validity (Resing et al., 2002).

Conclusion.

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The follow-up study revealed that students in the former experimental group achieved significantly higher results in reading comprehension. The findings suggest that an improvement in metacognitive skills correlates with enhanced reading comprehension. Despite prevailing beliefs among teachers and some researchers that reading comprehension primarily depends on abilities such as intelligence, our results indicate that it can be taught and learned. Reading comprehension is not solely determined by fixed and unchangeable abilities; rather, teachers have the potential to impart metacognitive knowledge to their students.

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